

IMPACT OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS' SELF-EFFICACY ON THEIR OCCUPATIONAL COMMITMENT IN BALOCHISTAN, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

This quantitative study investigates effects of self-efficacy on occupational commitment of teachers in Balochistan. The study's objectives are to find out opinion of teachers about their self-efficacy on occupational commitment. A quantitative, non-experimental, predictive correlational research design was used to achieve the study's objectives. Government secondary-school teachers and students of Balochistan are selected for this study. A sample of 640 teachers and 640 students is selected through a multistage sampling technique. The Teacher Self-efficacy Scale developed by Tschannen-Moran and Hoy (2001), and self-developed questionnaire of occupational commitment are used for the collection of data. Likewise, a multiple regression model is also used to explore the effects of self-efficacy of teachers on occupational commitment. For reliability and validity of the data, the self-developed questionnaire was sent to experts for review and pilot test. Descriptive statistics mean and standard deviation determined respondents' perceptions of self-efficacy and occupational commitment. This study results indicate significant effects of self-efficacy on occupational commitment. It is important because self-efficacy is required to upgrade teaching standards of teachers.

Keywords: Assessing, Impact, Teachers, Self-efficacy and Occupational Commitment

INTRODUCTION

A comprehensive educational system is viewed as foundation of a developing country (Jourdan et al., 2021). The realization of such an educational system largely depends on teachers, thereby making teaching profession more challenging and demanding (Kulikowski et al., 2022). Due to teachers' multiple duties and obligations, this profession is quite challenging; teachers are tasked with delivering lessons and managing classrooms, fulfilling grading assignments, attending meetings, and engaging in professional development activities (Brammer & Clark, 2020). Certain teachers experience performance-impacting stress, and the pressure to perform well can lead to increased stress levels, affecting the ability of teachers to impart quality instruction (Lennox, 2020). Regarding professional dedication and performance, this profession incorporates certain crucial elements, including self-efficacy, job stress, and emotional intelligence (Ochoa Pacheco et al., 2023). According to Jena (2022), someone who lacks emotional control while interacting with people is less driven to complete a task or do a decent job; as a result, that person cannot be viewed as a successful professional individual. However, Aboramadan (2022) pointed occupational commitment is crucial to the responsibilities of a devoted educator. Eyüp (2022) also underlined persistent stress

could impair educators' mental and physical health and impact their dedication to the quality of instruction.

Occupational commitment as a dependent variable has three elements; affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment (Meyer & Allen, 1991). Moreover, Panda et al. (2022) defined normative commitment as an obligation of the staff to provide clients with competent service. According to Meyer and Allen (1991), an affective commitment attitude is a good association between individual activities and opportunities, while continuance commitment evaluates the employees' advantages and disadvantages regarding their willingness to retain their work in the organization. Even though organizational commitment has many dimensions, only certain types of study have focused on those three elements. Most studies examined emotions' impact and continued commitment (Wang & Hu, 2022). When employees feel supported by the business, their contributions and commitment to the company will be even more spectacular (Saadeh & Suifan, 2020). Support from the organization may increase their dedication to work. The significance increases with favorable working circumstances (Palumbo, 2020).

When teachers receive support from educational institutions, such as resources, professional development opportunities, and a positive work environment, it increases their dedication to work (Abdulaziz et al., 2022). This level of education is greatly affected by quality of teaching. Teacher performance as educators can contribute to high or low-quality of education. Performance is an outcome and work conduct attained to fulfil the duties and obligations within a predetermined time frame (Taryana et al., 2023). Although studies like (Maheshwari, 2022) have been conducted on physical factors to judge their influence on teachers' commitment and performance, but less attention have given to the inclusion of psychological factors such as Self-efficacy, job stress and emotional intelligence influencing occupational commitment and performance of secondary school teachers (Cayupe., et al 2023).

Scientists and governments have long valued teachers as a vital component of the educational process (Gamage et al., 2022). Interaction between students and teachers plays a crucial role in learning and teaching activities, information acquisition, and personality development of students (Feraco et al., 2023). Thus, the government prioritized teacher reform to enhance Pakistani education (Iftikhar et al., 2022). In Pakistan, there is still a need for improvement concerning teacher competency, knowledge, and pedagogical ability (Asad et al., 2022). According to the 2019 results of the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) study, Pakistan continues to have the lowest levels of literacy, science, and mathematics education worldwide (Ahmad et al., 2022). The imbalance and poor caliber of instructors are to blame for this. As instructors are crucial in managing learning environment that encourages students to participate actively in learning activities, their poor performance will influence various factors, including student accomplishment and learning process (McKnight et al., 2016).

Additionally, few studies paid attention to the contributions of psychological factor such as Self-efficacy influencing occupational commitment of secondary school teachers

(Cayupei., et al 2023). Therefore, the preliminary focus of this research was to the effects of Self-efficacy in light of influencing occupational commitment of teachers. As per knowledge of the researcher, no research has been found to address the effect of self-efficacy on occupational in Balochistan at any level. According to the previous studies, no research has been found to address the effect of self-efficacy on occupational commitment and performance. There has yet to be any current research looking at the factors in Balochistan's public secondary schools in Pakistan. The findings of this research might be applied by educational institutions, particularly in Balochistan, Pakistan, to boost teachers' professionalism and dedication as leading resources in schools.

The particular effect of secondary school teachers' self-efficacy on occupational commitment is still needs to be discovered despite a sizable body of studies on the numerous elements influencing their occupational commitment. In this connection, each component has been investigated separately (Rosario et al., 2009). However, the simultaneous effect of this variables on secondary school teachers has yet to be well studied in the literature. It is essential to comprehend how these elements affect occupational commitment (Jamil et al., 2023).

The study selected Balochistan as a research location based on its educational context, Population diversity, access to participants and the prior research gap in the study field. Balochistan, the largest province in Pakistan in terms of area, is home to a diverse population. Researchers can gather valuable data from various teachers with varying backgrounds, experiences, and cultural contexts by conducting the study in Balochistan. This diversity can enhance the generalizability of the study's findings to a broader population. The province also has a wide range of challenges in its educational system, which makes it an exciting and relevant setting for this study.

The researcher has established connections with educational institutions in Balochistan, making it easier to access and recruit participants for the study. There is a need to do more research on the specified topic about Balochistan or similar regions. By conducting study in Balochistan, the researcher addresses a research gap and contributes to the literature on effects of self-efficacy on occupational commitment, specifically in the context of secondary school teachers in Balochistan.

There are inconsistencies in previous studies and scarcity of researchers on describing the association among school teachers' self-efficacy and occupational commitment. The researcher did not find studies related to these variables in terms of the kind of relationship being addressed in this study in particular. Therefore, this study is crucial to the understanding of self-efficacy and occupational commitment of secondary school teachers.

Statement of the Problem

This study is essential because teachers' self-efficacy may affect their feelings, behaviors and attitudes concerning teachers' occupational commitment. A lack of proficiency in this

regard may stem from those who struggle with low self-efficacy are more likely to ignore and undervalue the teaching profession.

The problem statement concerning this endeavor is to find the effects of secondary school teachers' self-efficacy on their occupational commitment. Specifically, this study explores how these factors affect teachers' commitment to their profession and their effectiveness in performing their duties.

Therefore, this study aims to investigate the combined effects of teacher self-efficacy on occupational commitment among teachers. By examining these effects, the study aims to contribute to the existing literature and provides practical implications for educational institutions to enhance teachers' occupational commitment.

Research Questions

Following are the research questions of the study:

1. What are teachers' perceptions about their self-efficacy and occupational commitment?
2. How do teachers' self-efficacy effect their occupational commitment?

Hypotheses of the Study

H. Self-efficacy (factors) has significant effect on occupational commitment (factors).

- Ha. Student engagement has significant effect on continuance commitment of teachers.
- Hb. Student engagement has significant effect on affective commitment of teachers.
- Hc. Student engagement has significant effect on normative commitment of teachers.
- Hd. Instructional strategy has significant effect on continuance commitment of teachers.
- He. Instructional strategy has significant effect on affective commitment of teachers.
- Hf. Instructional strategy has significant effect on normative commitment of teachers
- Hg. Classroom environment has significant effect on continuance commitment of teachers.
- Hh. Classroom environment has significant effect on affective commitment of teachers.
- Hi. Classroom environment has significant effect on normative commitment of teachers.

Significance of the Study

Effective teachers give students a wealth of information and knowledge during their lessons to improve their educational outcomes. This makes a teacher's self-efficacy a crucial construct that provides immediate and persuasive responses to students. High self-efficacy teachers use cutting-edge pedagogical methods of modern era. They help mediocre learners and are mainly concerned with social development of the students. High-performing teachers anticipate that their students will take ownership of their

accomplishments in academic achievements. They firmly believe that learning and mutual support to the students would multiply pupils' academic achievements.

This study mainly investigates the effect of teacher self-efficacy and occupational commitment, in secondary school teachers of Balochistan. The main aim of this study is to add the recent literature on teacher self-efficacy and occupational commitment. The current study may create awareness among teachers, students, administration and other stakeholders of the education department. This study may help school education department work on teachers' capabilities and relevant issues. This study may also help concerned authorities in finding factors affecting teaching and learning matters in Balochistan.

Delimitations of the Study

The study needed deep investigation, but due to time and financial reasons, it was delimited to feasibility, accessibility, and interest in exploring the unique context of that particular province. This study was delimited to

1. The province of Balochistan, Pakistan.
2. The public sector secondary schools of Balochistan.
3. The secondary school teachers of Balochistan.
4. The class tenth students of Balochistan.

Limitations of the Study

- 1) The researchers faced difficulty to collect the required information from the teachers.
- 2) Since the study is delimited to the public sector secondary schools therefore, there may be question of generalization of the results for entire secondary schools of Balochistan.
- 3) Only questionnaires are used to conduct this study.
- 4) The research design in this study is quantitative, and data is collected from the teachers and students of secondary schools in Balochistan Province.
- 5) Social Biases may also affect the result of the study.

METHODOLOGY

Research philosophy

Positivism, constructionism, pragmatism, and advocacy/participatory research are the four basic philosophical orientations in educational research (Creswell, 2003). For mixed-method studies, pragmatism is advised because it focuses on practical, problem centric, action oriented and utility oriented. While advocacy/participatory is employed in studies that focus on marginalized people and address issues of political and social injustices. This paradigm allows understanding of people's perspective as it is based on social reality and tries to find out real solution of original problem to ensure desirable change (Leavy,

2022). Constructionism is ideal for qualitative research investigations (Creswell, 2003). This research paradigm also emphasizes the significance of context and culture in the creation and accumulation of knowledge. Constructivist study seeks to comprehend specific circumstances or events. Ideas can be created from the rich data that is acquired. Research on group interactions primarily addresses the social issues facing the target group (Burns et al., 2022). The positivist approach is appropriate for quantitative studies that aim to validate theory or a model through empirical observations and measurements. According to the positivism approach, there are always causes that result in particular effects or outcomes. As a result, this study is based on positivist knowledge claims because it is the paradigm that best fits the needs of the proposed research.

Research Design

Different study designs can be used by researchers in applying quantitative and qualitative methodologies. Experimental, non-experimental, survey, and correlational research designs are some of the most common ones employed in quantitative research (Creswell, 2012). The designs are chosen in accordance with the study's goals and purpose. In order to determine the effects of teachers' self-efficacy and occupational commitment in Balochistan, quantitative, non-experimental, predictive correlational research design was used in this study (Creswell, 2018).

Population of the Research Study

In this study, the population comprised 6163 teachers as per Balochistan Education Statistics (BES, 2021-22) while the population of those students who appeared in the Balochistan Board of Intermediate and Secondary Education (BBISE) annual tenth class board examination. Their total population was 63506 (BBISE, 2022).

Table 1: Population of the students in the study

	Boys	Girls	Total
	41140	22366	63506
Grand Total			63506

Table 2: Population of the teachers in the study

	Male	Female	Total
	725	2438	6163
Grand Total			6163

Sample and sampling techniques of the study

Sample determines the precise number of sample sizes for the population that is available online (Krejcie & Morgan, 1970). The ideal sample size to use, according to Krejcie and Morgan (1970), is 382, and the appropriate sample size is 384 when the population is 1000,000. To ensure that the results of statistical algorithms were appropriate, a sample size of 640 teachers and 640 students was chosen for the investigation. This was done based on comparisons among the studies by Krejcie and Morgan (1970).

According to Sekaran (2003), sampling should be done correctly to offer each population component equal and parallel representation. Sekaran (2003) asserts that probability and non-probability are the two groups of techniques of sampling; these are further divided into additional designs (Sekaran, 2003). Each sampling strategy has benefits and drawbacks. The researcher chose a sampling design based on the relevant population and the purpose of the study. Sekaran (2003) asserts that simple random sampling is adequate since it accurately represents the entire population. Because of this, the design of a simple random sample is compelling and appropriate for investigation. Because of this, the study at hand used primary random sampling.

In this investigation, a multistage sampling technique was applied. In the first step, eight divisional headquarters were chosen. This method made the researcher choose a sample from the desired population based on accessibility and willingness to participate. A simple random sampling technique is used to select schools during the second stage. Thirdly, a stratified random sampling technique is used to select students and teachers. The stratified random sampling method entails randomly selecting a reasonably large number of units from the population or from particular subgroups (strata) of a population (Etikan & Bala, (2017), and fourth and lastly, the simple random sampling technique is used in each school in the selection of students.

Krejcie and Morgan (1970) determined that a sample size of 622 is ideal for a population of 10,000, while a sample size of 646 is appropriate for populations of 25,000/-, with degree of confidence 99%, and margin of error 5%. The researcher chose a sample size of 640 because under-consideration population is 14046; this sample is easily dividable, does not pose a problem for data collection, and represents the sample equally.

In the current investigation, a stratified sampling strategy is adopted. The researcher chose equal-sized samples from several subgroups, including male and female, rural and urban. Gay (2000) claims that identical subgroups (male, female, rural and urban) are sampled using the stratified sampling technique. Subgroups are equally represented in the sample as they are in the population. They can also be employed with equal-sized samples from each of the subgroups if comparisons between various subgroups are necessary.

Table 3: Sector-wise sample of the teachers

	Male	Female	Total
Urban	160	160	320
Rural	160	160	320
Grand Total			640

Table 3 indicates that the total strength of the teachers is 320, whereas 160 male and 160 female teachers participated in the study, thus making a total of 640 teachers.

Table 4: Sector-wise sample of the students

	Boys	Girls	Total
Urban	160	160	320
Rural	160	160	320
Grand Total			640

Table 3 indicates that the total strength of students is 320, whereas 160 boys and 160 girls participated in the study, thus making a total of 640 students.

Research Instruments

This study used two different questionnaires for data collection. These questionnaires are (a) Self-efficacy (b)Occupational commitment

Questionnaire for Teachers About Their Self-efficacy

The researcher adapted the self-efficacy tool developed by Tschannen-Moran and Hoy (2001). This tool was also translated into Urdu. This questionnaire comprised 24 items.

The lengthy form of Tschannen-Moran and Hoy's (2001) Teachers Self-Efficacy Scale is used to gather information from teachers. According to Tschannen-Mora and Hoy (2001), an instrument is used in classrooms worldwide to test instructors' perceived skills. The factor-wise reliability of the instrument is judged by calculating Cronbach's alpha values 0.861, 0.816, and 0.799. Researchers obtained data while upholding ethical standards.

Questionnaire for Teachers about their occupational commitment

This questionnaire included total of 13 items on a five-point scale made up the survey. Teachers were asked to answer questions about their professional commitment to their organizations in a questionnaire.

Translation of the Instrument

The research instruments used in this study comprised self-efficacy, job stress, emotional intelligence, occupational commitment, and performance. A back translation method is used to translate these instruments into Urdu, the national language of Pakistan (Rehman, 1997).

Pilot Study

A pilot study is one of the most essential phases of a research effort (Barnett, 2018). Before implementation of investigation, it is undertaken to identify potential issue areas and weaknesses in the soundness and consistency of the research instruments and methodology (Faizi, 2020). Self-developed questionnaire was sent to professionals for review to determine their face validity and content validity. The surveys underwent a pilot test with 50 secondary school teachers to determine their reliability and Cronbach's alpha coefficient.

Validity of the Research Instruments

The authenticity of the objects cannot be determined just by the variables' dependability. The researcher must establish the validity of the research instrument's variables. Therefore, evaluating the reliability of the study's items and variables is crucial. Sekaran (2003) asserts that ensuring validity entails guaranteeing the precise measurement of the target idea. Creswell (2012) defined validity as the capacity to derive meaningful and practical inferences from the results of the instruments. The following types of validity were adhered to during this investigation.

Reliability of Instruments

Sekaran (2003) defined reliability as the degree of generating comparable results when repeated repeatedly under the same circumstances. It is denoted by (α). According to the setting of Balochistan, the teacher efficacy scale created by Tschannen, Moran, and Hoy (2001) was used in Urdu. Therefore, the coefficient of reliability is calculated in order to assess the instrument's (Urdu version) reliability.

Reliability coefficient of factors of self- efficacy

Cronbach's alpha is calculated using SPSS software. The alpha coefficient, in general, is 0.93. Three sub-factor's alpha reliability coefficients are shown:

Table 5

Factors	Number of statements	Reliability
Classroom management	08	0.79
Student engagement	08	0.82
Instructional strategies	08	0.86

Table 5 indicates that the Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient of classroom management is 0.79, student engagement is 0.82, and instructional strategies are 0.86.

Reliability coefficient of the factors of occupational commitment

The Cronbach Alpha coefficient for occupational commitment, in general, is 0.87, while three sub-factors of occupational commitment has the following alpha reliability coefficients:

Table 6

Factors	Number of Statements	Reliability
Affective commitment	4	0.84
Continuance Commitment	5	0.80
Normative Commitment	4	0.82

Table 6 indicates that the Cronbach Alpha Reliability Coefficient of the factors of occupational commitment is as follows. The affective commitment has 0.84, continuance commitment has 0.80, and normative commitment has 0.82.

Data Collection

In order to administer the questionnaires and obtain the required response rate, the researcher travelled around the target area. The sample locations in the province required the researcher to get there personally. The effectiveness of the tools translated by the researcher in the Urdu language, suggested by Tschannen-Moran and Hoy (2001), was utilized by the researcher to gather teachers' opinions on their efficacy views. The other questionnaire translated into Urdu under Balochistan's local conditions were occupational commitment. As a result, the researcher had to make multiple attempts to gather data from remote areas of Balochistan. Six days a week for eight weeks, the data was gathered. While student feedback was used to get information on teachers' performance, teacher feedback was also used to gather information about teachers' self-efficacy and occupational commitment.

Data Analysis

The suggested study's data analysis was built on two pillars. In the first base, respondents' perceptions of their self-efficacy and occupational commitment were assessed using descriptive analysis, such as mean and standard deviation. Multiple linear regression was used to determine the effect of teachers' self-efficacy on their occupational commitment.

Descriptive statistics

Sekaran (2003) asserts that descriptive statistics aid in organizing the data, summarizing it meaningfully, and making it simple to comprehend. As a result, the researcher calculated the frequency distribution, arithmetic mean, and standard deviation and used tests of internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha) to know about the perceptions of teachers and students about the study's variables.

Inferential Statistics

Regarding data comparison through analysis, inferential statistics is particularly interested in the link between two variables, the variations in a variable between distinct subgroups, and how numerous independent factors may explain the variance in a dependent variable (Sekaran,2003).

Regression analysis

Multiple regression analysis is used to investigate the simultaneous effects of numerous independent factors on a dependent variable that is interval scaled. In other words, multiple regression analysis assists in determining the extent to which a set of predictors may account for the variance in the dependent variable (Sekaran, 2003).

Two or more factors' known and distinct effects on a dependent variable are analyzed via multiple regression (Mood, 2010). It is also used to determine how much one variable can be predicted by a group of competing variables (Guyatt et al., 1995). In order to determine if the chosen sources of stress statistically significantly explain the variance in work

engagement, job satisfaction, and desire to quit, respectively, multiple regression was performed.

Data Analysis

Table 7: Description of the variables

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Self-efficacy	640	4.2072	0.38021
Occupational commitment	640	4.1478	0.53905
Valid N (list-wise)	640		

Table 7 shows the descriptive statistics of the study variables, which summarizes the averages of the field data. The mean observed value of Self Efficacy is 4.2072 with a Standard Deviation of 0.38021. This means that most observed values revolve around its mean. The mean value of occupational commitment is 4.1478, and the standard deviation is 0.53905. The mean performance value is 4.1621, and the standard deviation is 0.45064.

Table 8: Description of the factors of self-Efficacy

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Efficacy in student engagement	640	4.1447	0.45197
Efficacy instructional strategy	640	4.2508	0.43470
Efficacy in classroom management	640	4.2404	0.39736
Valid N (list-wise)	640		

Table 8 contains the numerical data representing a set of values showing the different factors of self-efficacy, whereby the data set revolves around a central mean. The mean observed value of Self-Efficacy in student engagement is 4.1447 with a Standard Deviation of 0.45197. The mean observed value of self-efficacy in instructional strategy is 4.2508, with and Standard deviation of 0.43470; the mean observed value of Efficacy in classroom management is 4.2405, and the Standard deviation is 0.39736, which means that the majority of observed values revolve around its mean.

Table 9: Description of the factors of occupational commitment

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Affective Commitment	640	4.2016	0.62983
Continuance Commitment	640	3.8947	0.68553
Normative Commitment	640	4.3073	0.56155
Valid N (list-wise)	640		

Table 9 indicates the Mean and Standard deviation of Affective Commitment, Continuance, and Normative commitment collectively acting as components of occupational commitment. The average affective commitment is observed at 4.2016 with a standard deviation of 0.62983, indicating the presence of specific values above or below the average level of values. The Average of Continuance has a Mean value of 3.8947 and a standard deviation of 0.68553, representing the impact of extreme values on the variable's mean. The average normative commitment has a mean value of 4.3073 and a standard deviation of 0.56155.

Assumptions of Multiple Linear Regression

To answer the research question, what are the effects of self-efficacy, job stress, and emotional intelligence on occupational commitment, and performance? The multiple linear regression model (MLRM) is used to investigate the predicted effect of self-efficacy, job stress, and emotional intelligence on occupational commitment, and performance.

Considering this, the assumptions associated with using the regression model were studied. Gelman (2020) and Kuha (2020) proposed that before utilizing MLR analyses, the following assumptions be verified.

Dependent Variable-There is just one dependent variable that must be determined at the continuous level. This prediction was confirmed when the total scores of the dependent variable occupational commitment and performance at secondary school level were calculated on a continuous scale.

Independent variable- In this study there are three independent variables such as factors of self-efficacy, job stress, and emotional intelligence and two dependent variables that are occupational commitment, and performance. While only two independent variables are required that must be measured in continuous or nominal scale.

Homoscedasticity-This indicates possible relationship by evaluating a secondary regression where self-efficacy, job stress and emotional intelligence is the residuals (Ugwuanyi et al., 2020). By using estimates in terms of co-efficient, Glejser test is used to find out heteroscedastic, when the value of significance is greater up to 0.05 make the data homoscedastic.

Heteroscedasticity- When the value of independent variable is less than 0.05.

Normality curve- In the study this assumption shows that the underlying residuals are normally distributed, or approximately so.

Autocorrelation- The Durbin-Watson test is used to determine observational independence. The value, larger than the lower limit of 1.5 but less than 2. as the absence of autocorrelation. This shows that no autocorrelation exists.

Linearity- A linear relationship was found between independent and dependent variables. Scatterplot is used for the verification of the relationship. In this relationship residual cure were plotted.

Multicollinearity -The multicollinearity is required to be absent in multiple linear regression which can be tested using VIF values. As claimed by Stevens (2009), the Value VIFs should be less than 10 which show a low linear relationship connection between the independent variables. Low VIF values (each was less than 10), verify assumption that there is no multicollinearity.

Figure 1: Data without outliers for the independent variables self-efficacy and dependent variables occupational commitment.

Figure 2: Histograms for the independent variables self-efficacy, job stress, and emotional intelligence and dependent variables occupational commitment, and performance

Table 10: Effect of factors of self-efficacy on affective commitment

Model	USC		SC	t-value	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.649	0.257		6.418	0.000
SE	0.202	0.083	0.145	2.441	0.015
IS	0.400	0.084	0.276	4.781	0.000
CE	0.004	0.089	0.003	0.046	0.964
R=0.397	R. square=.157	Adj.R sq=.153	F=39.68	α =0.000	
Durban Watson=1.606, VIF=1.683, 1.603, 1.60					

Table 10 shows that the value of R is 0.397, which depicts that students' engagements and instructional strategy are the factors of self-efficacy, have a highly significant relation with affective commitment of teachers while classroom environment has no significant effect on affective commitment. Affective commitment is factor of occupational commitment. The R² value is 0.157, showing that students engagements, instructional strategy and classroom management explains 15.7% of the variability in affective commitment. For homoscedastic, p should be greater than 0.05, here p is less than 0.05 for SE and IS so Heteroscedasticity. While for CM, the value of VIF should be less than 10, here value is 1 multicollinearity. The F=39.68 and the alpha value shows that accurate expectation and profound influence of the model is made. The value of beta β (slop of coefficient) for self-efficacy (SE) and (IS) 0.145 and 0.276, t for SE and IS (2.441 and

4.781) respectively having p less than 0.05 therefore, changes in depending variable affective commitment are statistically significant. While the CM is 0.964 having p greater than 0.05 therefore change in dependent variable 'affective commitment' is not statistically significant

Figure 3: Effect of factors of self-efficacy on affective commitment

Table 11: Effect of factors of self-efficacy on continuance commitment

Model	USC		SC	t-value	Sig.
	B	Std. Er	Beta		
Constant	1.228	0.280		4.380	.000
SE	0.170	0.090	0.112	1.879	.061
IS	0.507	0.091	0.321	5.558	.000
CE	0.045	0.097	0.026	0.461	.645
R=.392 R sq=.153, Adj R Sq=.149, F=38.50, α =0.000, Durbin Watson=1.407 VIF=1.683, 1.603, 1.645					

Table 11 shows that student engagement and classroom environment have no significant effect on continuance commitment while instructional strategy has significant effect on continuance commitment. The value of R is 0.392, The R² value is 0.153, showing that students engagements, instructional strategy and classroom management explains 15.3% of the variability in continuance commitment. For homoscedastic p should be greater than 0.05, here p is greater than 0.05. For SE and CE, so the p value of (IS) is less than 0.05 that is heteroscedastic. The value of VIF should be less than 10; here values are 1.683, 1.603 and 1.645, so no multicollinearity. The F=38.50 and the alpha value show that accurate expectation and profound influence of the model is made. The value of beta β (slop of coefficient) for self-efficacy (IS) 0.321, t for IS (5.558) respectively having p less than 0.05 therefore, changes in depending variable continuance commitment are statistically significant. While the (SE) and (CM) are (1.112 and 0.226) and t values are (1.879 and 0.461) having p greater than 0.05 therefore change in depending variable continuance commitment is not statistically significant.

Figure 4: Effect of factors of self-efficacy on continuous commitment

Table 12: Effect of factors of self-efficacy on normative commitment

Model	USC		SC	t-value	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	2.320	0.233		9.944	0.000
SE	0.174	0.075	0.140	2.320	0.021
IS	0.334	0.076	0.259	4.405	0.000
CE	0-.037	0.081	0.026	0.454	0.650
R=.355	R sq=.126	Adj r Sq=.122	F=30.64,	$\alpha=0.000$	
Durban Watson=1.494, VIF=1.683, 1.603, 1.645					

Table 12 shows that student engagement and instructional strategy has significant effect on normative commitment while classroom environment has no significant effect on normative commitment. The value of R is 0.355, the R² value is 0.126, showing that students engagements, instructional strategy and classroom management explains 12.6% of the variability in normative commitment. For homoscedastic p should be greater than 0.05, here p is greater than 0.05 for (CM) so the p value of (SE and) (IS) is less than 0.05 that is heteroscedastic. The value of VIF should be less than 10 here values are 1.683, 1.603 and 1.645 so no multicollinearity. The F=30.64 and the alpha value shows that accurate expectation and profound influence of the model, is made. The value of beta β (slop of coefficient) for self-efficacy (SE) and (IS) 0.140 and 0.259, t for (SE) and (IS) (2.320 and 4.405) respectively having p less than 0.05, therefore, changes in depending variable normative commitment are statistically significant. While the (CM) is 0.026 and the t is 0.454 having p (0.650) greater than 0.05, therefore, change in depending variable normative commitment is not statistically significant.

Figure 5: Effect of factors of self-efficacy on normative commitment

DISCUSSION

The study's primary goal is to ascertain the effect of secondary school teachers' self-efficacy on their occupational commitment. The study uses mean and standard deviation to measure central tendency and dispersion. Regression analysis was also performed to determine the characteristics of the study variables.

This research concludes that the student engagement has a significant effect on the factor of dependent variable occupational commitment that is affective commitment. Furthermore, these variables have a weak positive relationship in the study conducted by Almutairi (2020), thus confirming this study's outcome. Student engagement has a weak positive relationship with affective commitment in the study conducted by Prifti (2022), while it has a negative relationship with affective commitment in the study conducted by Chigeda (2022). The factor of self-efficacy instructional strategy has significant effect on affective commitment. The instructional strategy has a significant effect on affective commitment, which is also the case in the study conducted by Donkor (2022), while it has a weak negative relationship in the study conducted by Habieb et al (2013) and Yildirim (2015). There is statistically significant effect of Instructional strategy on affective commitment in this study, that is also the case in the study being conducted by Brooks, Korzaan et al (2021) and Donkor (2022), in another study instructional strategy has negative effect on affective commitment in the research conducted by Demir (2020) and Akhtar (2013). Similarly, there is no significant effect of classroom engagement on normative commitment while the same variable has a weak negative relationship with each other in the study conducted by Demir (2020) and Akhtar (2013). There is no significant effect of classroom engagement on normative commitment (Pratama et al., 2022). The factor of self-efficacy student engagement has no significant effect on continuance commitment. Continuance commitment is the factor of occupational commitment, while the same variable has a weak negative relationship with each other in the study of Salas-Pilco et al (2022). There is significant effect of classroom engagement

on continuance commitment (Bowden et al., 2021). There is no significant effect of classroom environment on continuance commitment. Continuance commitment is the factor of occupational commitment while the same variable has a weak negative relationship with each other in the study of Serhan et al (2022). On the other hand, there is significant effect of classroom environment on continuance commitment (San-Martín et al., 2020).

Instructional strategy which is the factor of self-efficacy has significant effect on continuance commitment which is the factor of dependent variable occupational commitment. There is no significant effect of instructional strategy with the same variable in the study conducted by Cesinger et al (2023) while there is significant effect of instructional strategy on continuance commitment (Ying et al., 2023). There is significant effect of student engagement on normative commitment which is the factor of dependent variable occupational commitment. There is no significant effect of student engagement with the same variable in the study of Love (2022) while there is significant effect of student engagement on normative commitment (Pratama et al., 2022). There is significant effect of classroom environment on normative commitment which is the factor of dependent variable occupational commitment. There is no significant effect of classroom environment with the same variable in the study conducted by Atika (2022), while there is significant effect of classroom room environment on normative commitment (Demir et al., 2022). Instructional strategy has no statistical significance on normative commitment. Normative commitment is the factor of occupational commitment while the same variable has a weak negative relationship with each other in the study of Huynh et al. (2023). There is significant effect of instructional strategy on normative commitment (San-Martín et al., 2020).

CONCLUSION

The research explores the effect of secondary school teachers' self-efficacy on their occupational commitment. Standard deviation, mean, and regression analysis are used in this study to analyze the data. In this study questionnaires are used for data collection, and descriptive and inferential statistics are used to analyze the data. The effect of the variables in the study is discussed. This study is, quantitative, non-experimental, predictive correlational research design is used (Creswell, 2018). The research design used is a predictive correlational research design. The population of the study is 6163 secondary school teachers teaching 10th grade in public sector secondary schools in Balochistan. The total strength of the 9th-grade students is 63506 who appeared in the Annual 2022. This quantitative study investigates the effect of teacher self-efficacy, job stress, and emotional intelligence on occupational commitment and performance in Balochistan.

This study concludes that there is significant effect of the factor of self-efficacy student engagement and instructional strategy on the factor of dependent variable occupational commitment that is affective commitment. While the other factor of self-efficacy that is classroom environment has no statistically significant on the factor of dependent variable

effective commitment. There is no statistically significant effect of student engagement and classroom environment on continuance commitment. While, there is statistically significant effect of instructional strategy on continuance commitment. There is statistically significant effect of student engagement and classroom environment on normative commitment. There is no statistically significant effect of instructional strategy on normative commitment.

Recommendations

Enhancing Self-Efficacy- It was found that self-efficacy has significant effect on occupational commitment and performance. Therefore, it is recommended that professional development programs in educational institutions shall prioritize the implementation of professional development programs that may enhance and strengthen teachers' self-efficacy. These programs may help teachers to reflect on their teaching practices, acquire new instructional strategies, and receive feedback and support from mentors or instructional coaches. By enhancing teachers' belief in their abilities, these programs can promote their commitment to the profession and improve their overall performance.

Supportive Work Environment- Creating a supportive work environment is essential for nurturing teachers' self-efficacy. Educational institutions should foster a culture that values and recognizes teachers' contributions. Providing opportunities for collaboration, mentorship, and peer support can boost teachers' confidence and self-efficacy. Additionally, reducing administrative burdens, providing adequate resources, and promoting a positive school environment can alleviate unnecessary stressors and enhance teachers' commitment and performance.

Mentoring and role modeling- Establishing mentoring programs where experience teachers serve as mentors to new teachers. Mentors can provide guidance, share their expertise, and be positive role models, enhancing new teachers' self-efficacy. Moreover, promoting peer observation and collaboration among teachers can facilitate the sharing of effective teaching practices and contribute to the development of self-efficacy among all teachers.

Future Research

A study on the same topic is suggested by using the qualitative or mixed method approach.

Reference

- 1) Abdulaziz, A., Bashir, M., & Alfalih, A. A. (2022). The impact of work-life balance and work overload on teacher's organizational commitment: do Job Engagement and Perceived Organizational support matter. *Education and Information Technologies*, 27(7), 9641-9663.
- 2) Abdullah, M. R., & Marican, S. (2020). Supervisory support and organizational citizenship behaviour: the role of self-efficacy as mediator. *International Journal of Public Sector Performance Management*, 6(6), 854-875.
- 3) Ahmad, S., Rodrigues, S., & Bhutta, S. M. (2022). Pakistan's First Ever Participation in International Large-Scale Assessment (TIMSS): Critique and Implications. *Journal of Education and Educational Development*, 9(2), 191-210.
- 4) Akhtar, S., Ghayas, S., & Adil, A. (2013). Self-efficacy and optimism as predictors of organizational commitment among bank employees. *International Journal of Research Studies in Psychology*, 2(2), 33-42.
- 5) Almutairi, Y. M. N. (2020). Leadership self-efficacy and organizational commitment of faculty members: Higher education. *Administrative Sciences*, 10(3), 66.
- 6) Asad, M. M., Rind, A. A., & Abdulmuhsin, A. A. (2022). The effect of knowledge management in educational settings: a study of education management organizations (EMOs) schools of Pakistan. *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*, 30(5), 1156-1171.
- 7) Bowden, J. L. H., Tickle, L., & Naumann, K. (2021). The four pillars of tertiary student engagement and success: a holistic measurement approach. *Studies in Higher Education*, 46(6), 1207-1224.
- 8) Brammer, S., & Clark, T. (2020). COVID-19 and management education: Reflections on challenges, opportunities, and potential futures. *British journal of Management*, 31(3), 453.
- 9) Brooks, N. G., Korzaan, M. L., & Brooks, S. (2021). Normative commitment in an information systems project environment. *International Journal of Managing Projects in Business*, 14(3), 563-579.
- 10) Burns, M., Bally, J., Burles, M., Holtslander, L., & Peacock, S. (2022). Constructivist grounded theory or interpretive phenomenology? Methodological choices within specific study contexts. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 21, 16094069221077758.
- 11) Cayupe, J. C., Bernedo-Moreira, D. H., Morales-García, W. C., Alcaraz, F. L., Peña, K. B. C., Saintila, J., & Flores-Paredes, A. (2023). Self-efficacy, organizational commitment, workload as predictors of life satisfaction in elementary school teachers: the mediating role of job satisfaction. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14, 1066321.
- 12) Cesinger, B., Gundolf, K., Hughes, M., Khedhaouria, A., & Montani, F. (2023). The bright and dark sides of the Dark Triad traits among senior managers: effects on organizational commitment. *Review of Managerial Science*, 17(5), 1731-1763.
- 13) Chigeda, F., Ndofirepi, T. M., & Steyn, R. (2022). Continuance in organizational commitment: The role of emotional intelligence, work-life balance support, and work-related stress. *Global Business and Organizational Excellence*, 42(1), 22-38.
- 14) Creswell, J. W. (2003). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approach* (2nd ed.). SAGE Publications.
- 15) Creswell, J. W. (2012). *Educational research: Planning, conducting and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research* (4th ed.). Pearson Education Inc.
- 16) Creswell, J. W. (2018). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approach* (5th ed.). SAGE Publications.

- 17) Demir, S. (2020). The role of self-efficacy in job satisfaction, organizational commitment, motivation and job involvement. *Eurasian Journal of Educational Research*, 20(85), 205-224.
- 18) Donkor, F. (2022). Do Transformational Leaders Affect Employee Performance and Normative Commitment Through General Self-Efficacy? Analysis in Ghanaian Public Sector Organizations. *Public Organization Review*, 22(3), 707-723.
- 19) Etikan, I., & Bala, K. (2017). Sampling and sampling methods. *Biometrics & Biostatistics International Journal*, 5(6), 00149.
- 20) Eyüp, Y. U. R. T. (2022). Collective teacher self-efficacy and burnout: The mediator role of job satisfaction. *International Journal of Modern Education Studies*, 6(1), 51-69.
- 21) Faizi, A. J., & Jayesh, J. R. (2020). Developing of mode choice model for regular trips based on the pilot study. *International Journal of Engineering Applied Science and Technology*, 4(12), 153-158.
- 22) Feraco, T., Resnati, D., Fregonese, D., Spoto, A., & Meneghetti, C. (2023). An integrated model of school students' academic achievement and life satisfaction. Linking soft skills, extracurricular activities, self-regulated learning, motivation, and emotions. *European Journal of Psychology of Education*, 38(1), 109-130.
- 23) Gamage, K. A., Ekanayake, S. Y., & Dehideniya, S. C. (2022). Embedding sustainability in learning and teaching: Lessons learned and moving forward—approaches in STEM higher education programmes. *Education Sciences*, 12(3), 225.
- 24) Gay, L.R. (2000). *Educational Research: Competencies for Analysis and Application*. New York: Merrill Publishing Co.
- 25) Habieb, E. T. E. A., El-Shaer, A. M., Shrief, W. I., & Elsayed, N. M. (2013). Effect of faculty support, and nursing students' self-efficacy, and affective commitment on their academic achievements. *Life Science Journal*, 10(3), 2707-2716.
- 26) Huynh, T. H., Bui, T. Q., & Nguyen, P. N. (2023, March). How to foster the commitment level of managers? Exploring the role of moderators on the relationship between job satisfaction and organizational commitment: A study of educational managers in Vietnam. *In Frontiers in Education* (8)1140587.
- 27) Jamil, S. M., Shah, S.A., & Rehman, F. (2023) Impact of Mathematics anxiety on students 'academic achievement in undergraduate classes: A study of Balochistan, Pakistan. *Journal of Jilin University (Engineering and Technology Edition)* 42(5), 1-8
- 28) Jena, L. K. (2022). Does workplace spirituality lead to raising employee performance? The role of citizenship behavior and emotional intelligence. *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*, 30(6), 1309-1334.
- 29) Johnson, R. B., & Christensen, L. (2019). *Educational research: Quantitative, qualitative, and mixed approaches*. Sage Publications.
- 30) Krejcie, R. V., & Morgan, D. W. (1970). Determining sample size for research activities. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 30 (3), 607–610.
- 31) Kulikowski, K., Przytuła, S., & Sułkowski, Ł. (2022). E-learning? Never again! On the unintended consequences of COVID-19 forced e-learning on academic teacher motivational job characteristics. *Higher Education Quarterly*, 76(1), 174-189.
- 32) Leavy, P. (2022). *Research design: Quantitative, qualitative, mixed methods, arts-based, and community-based participatory research approaches*. Guilford Publications.
- 33) Lennox, J. (2020). *More working from home will change the shape and size of cities*. Centre of Policy Studies, Victoria University.

- 34) Love, K., Anderson, A., & Alamuri, N. (2022). The Relationship Between Student Engagement and Organizational Commitment Among College Students. *College Student Journal*, 56(3), 221-234.
- 35) Maheshwari, G. (2022). Influence of teacher-perceived transformational and transactional school leadership on teachers' job satisfaction and performance: a case of Vietnam. *Leadership and Policy in Schools*, 21(4), 876-890.
- 36) McKnight, K., O'Malley, K., Ruzic, R., Horsley, M. K., Franey, J. J., & Bassett, K. (2016). Teaching in a digital age: How educators use technology to improve student learning. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 48(3), 194-211.
- 37) Meyer, J. P., & Allen, N. J. (1991). A three-component conceptualization of organizational commitment. *Human Resource Management Review*, 1(1), 61-89.
- 38) Ochoa Pacheco, P., Coello-Montecel, D., & Tello, M. (2023). Psychological Empowerment and Job Performance: Examining Serial Mediation Effects of Self-Efficacy and Affective Commitment. *Administrative Sciences*, 13(3), 76.
- 39) Palumbo, R. (2020). Let me go to the office! An investigation into the side effects of working from home on work-life balance. *International Journal of Public Sector Management*, 33(6/7), 771-790
- 40) Panda, A., Jain, N. K., & Nambudiri, R. (2022). Work–family conflict, affective commitment, leadership and job satisfaction: a moderated mediation analysis. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 71(4), 1469-1489.
- 41) Pratama, E. N., Suwarni, E., & Handayani, M. A. (2022). The effect of job satisfaction and organizational commitment on turnover intention with person organization fit as moderator variable. *Aptisi Transactions on Management (ATM)*, 6(1), 74-82.
- 42) Prifti, R. (2022). Self–efficacy and student satisfaction in the context of blended learning courses. *Open Learning: The Journal of Open, Distance and e-Learning*, 37(2), 111-125.
- 43) Rahman, T. (1997). The medium of instruction controversy in Pakistan. *Journal of Multilingual and Multicultural Development*, 18(2), 145-154.
- 44) Rosario, M., Schrimshaw, E. W., & Hunter, J. (2009). Disclosure of sexual orientation and subsequent substance use and abuse among lesbian, gay, and bisexual youths: critical role of disclosure reactions. *Psychology of Addictive Behaviors*, 23(1), 175.
- 45) Saadeh, I. M., & Suifan, T. S. (2020). Job stress and organizational commitment in hospitals: The mediating role of perceived organizational support. *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*, 28(1), 226-242.
- 46) Salas-Pilco, S. Z., Yang, Y., & Zhang, Z. (2022). Student engagement in online learning in Latin American higher education during the COVID-19 pandemic: A systematic review. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 53(3), 593-619.
- 47) San-Martín, S., Jiménez, N., Rodríguez-Torrico, P., & Piñeiro-Ibarra, I. (2020). The determinants of teachers' continuance commitment to e-learning in higher education. *Education and Information Technologies*, 25(4), 3205-3225.
- 48) Sekaran, U. (2003). *Research method for business: A skill building approach* (4th ed.): John Wiley and Sons.
- 49) Serhan, C., Nehmeh, N., & Sioufi, I. (2022). Assessing the effect of organizational commitment on turnover intentions amongst Islamic bank employees. *ISRA International Journal of Islamic Finance*, 14(2), 141-156.

- 50) Taryana, T., Riniati, W. O., Al Haddar, G., Sembiring, D., & Mutmainnah, M. (2023). The Influence of Teacher Certification and Teaching Motivation on Teacher Performance. *Journal on Education*, 5(3), 6726-6735.
- 51) Tschannen-Moran, M., & Hoy, A. W. (2001). Teacher efficacy: Capturing an elusive construct. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 17(7), 783-805.
- 52) Wang, Q., Wang, J., Zhou, X., Li, F., & Wang, M. (2020). How inclusive leadership enhances follower taking charge: the mediating role of affective commitment and the moderating role of traditionality. *Psychology Research and Behavior Management*, 13, 1103-1114.
- 53) Yıldırım, I. (2015). The correlation between organizational commitment and occupational burnout among the physical education teachers: The mediating role of self-efficacy. *International Journal of Progressive Education*, 11(3), 119-130.